

Oxyfuel Biomethane Combustion and CO₂ Capture Pathways for Renewable Carbon Cycles in High-Temperature Industries

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With the Renewable Energy Act (EEG) phase-out, many German biogas plants face challenges to remain economically viable. This work explores the strategy of biogas upgrading via membrane separation and subsequent oxyfuel combustion. The purified biomethane can be injected into the gas grid, leaving behind a methane-lean off-gas stream. The oxy-combustion of the off-gas supported by electrolysis-derived oxygen is proposed to generate heat, eliminate NO_x and CO emissions, and capture CO₂. The approach aims to combine sector coupling with emission reduction technologies for a sustainable biogas utilization.

Motivation

- EEG phase-out put the economic viability of many German biogas plants at risk
 - Stricter regulations and reduced tariffs make refinancing and continued operation difficult
- Membrane separation enables biomethane injection into the gas grid, but leaves a methane-lean off-gas stream
- This off-gas currently has little use but contains energy potential that should be exploited
- Oxyfuel combustion, as a Carbon Capture technology, using electrolysis-derived oxygen can generate heat, eliminate NO_x/CO, and recycle CO₂
- The project (Figure 1) aims to develop a sustainable framework ensuring ecological and economic operation of existing plants

Figure 1: Schematic Overview of the Research Project

CCUS Possibilities

Figure 2: Overview of Carbon Capture Technologies

Overview of Carbon Capture Technologies (Figure 2)

- Pre-combustion capture:**
 - Fuel conversion (e.g., gasification) prior to combustion
 - CO₂ separated before energy release
- Post-combustion capture:**
 - CO₂ removal from flue gas after combustion
 - Typically based on absorption processes
- Oxy-fuel combustion:**
 - Combustion in O₂ / CO₂ atmosphere instead of air
 - Produces a CO₂-rich flue gas, simplifying separation

Process Integration Strategy

- Selection of oxy-fuel combustion as a core process
- Direct generation of highly concentrated CO₂ streams
- Reduction of downstream separation effort

Numerical Study

- For this study CHEMKIN simulations were performed using GRI-Mech 3.0 [1] under atmospheric conditions (296 K / 1 bar), varying fuel content and equivalence ratio
- Laminar burning velocity:** CHEMKIN LBV Calculator (Figure 3)
 - Higher CH₄ content in a leaner mixture leads to higher LBV

Figure 3: Effect of Methane Concentration and Equivalence Ratio on Laminar Burning Velocity

Experimental Investigation

Experimental Set-up

- For the experimental investigations, a modular high-temperature combustion chamber is employed (Figure 4)
 - Burner (up to 50 kW), various fuel blends and oxidizer
- Optical diagnostics: Laser-Induced Fluorescence (LIF) and CMOS camera system with beam splitter, UV lens, narrowband OH* filter, and image intensifier.
 - Tests with fuel containing 45-60 % CH₄ and 40-55 % CO₂ under oxyfuel conditions (oxidizer is 100 % O₂)
 - 10 kW, Lambda 1.1

Figure 4: Schematic of Combustion Chamber Including Flow Streams and Diagnostic Systems

Experimental Results (Figure 5)

- Pure CH₄ flame: high-temperature structure, stable flame front, laminar-like propagation, low fluctuation
- Addition of CO₂: colder flame, broader shape, increased turbulence and fluctuation intensity

Figure 5: LIF measurement results for three fuel mixtures

Conclusion

- The laminar burning velocity increases as the content of CH₄ increases and the amount of inert gas CO₂ decreases; that is due to higher reactivity and energy release of methane-rich mixtures, as well as the reduced diluting and heat-absorbing effect of CO₂. Lower CO₂ concentrations lead to higher flame temperatures
 - Numerically derived fuel contents and equivalence ratios need to be tested experimentally in combustion chamber with LIF and flue gas analysis
 - Insights in flow structure, dynamics, sufficiently high flame temperature, and emissions
 - Experimental investigation of biogas separation via membrane systems to assess practical feasibility and resulting gas composition → integration into oxy-fuel combustion
 - The development of this technology can enable the continued operations of existing biogas plants
- Oxyfuel combustion is a promising technology for creating a sustainable carbon cycle**

